

artemis

An integrated approach To improve the Environmental performance of smart cities

D2 | Data Management Plan

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

ADAI-LAETA	Association for the Development of Industrial Aerodynamics - Associated Laboratory of Energy, Transports and Aeronautics
BIA	Bolzano Institutional Archive
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DOC	Miscrosoft Word processing document file format
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	Data Management Plan
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
INE	Instituto Nacional de Estatística (National Statistics Institute in Portugal)
ISPAT	Istituto di Statistica della Provincia di Trento (Stastitics Institute of the Province of Trento)
ISTAT	Istituto Nazionale di Statistica (National Statistics Institute in Italy)
JPG	Joint Photographics (Experts) Group
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LCA	Life-Cycle Assessment
MFA	Material Flow Accounting
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
ORD	Open Research Data
PDF	Portable Document Format
TIF	Tagged Image (File) Format
TXT	Text file
UM	Urban Metabolism
USB	Universal Serial Bus
WP	Work Package
XLS	Microsoft Excel spreadsheet file format

Project abstract

The smart city concept has received increased attention from researchers and decision-makers across the EU. However, there is a gap between smart city research & practice, and environmental sustainability: to date, smart city projects have not adequately assessed the environmental impacts of their strategies, which remain largely unknown. Research is needed to provide empirical evidence, advanced tools and metrics that can support the design, implementation and evaluation of smart city strategies to improve urban environmental sustainability.

Research goals

ARTEMIS will investigate whether and how the smart city can improve the environmental performance of urban systems. The research aims to provide insight on key aspects in smart city strategies that can effectively reduce environmental impacts; a novel environmental impact assessment framework to support decision-making in smart city projects; and improved key performance indicators (KPIs) on environmental sustainability and circularity for smart cities.

Achieving the goals

ARTEMIS will develop an integrated framework coupling urban metabolism and life-cycle assessment, to estimate how strategies implemented in two EU-funded smart city projects (in Lisbon, Portugal, and Trento, Italy) have affected a wide set of environmental impacts, associated with urban systems. Drawing on the framework and results, KPIs will be provided to evaluate environmental sustainability in smart cities. The framework, recommendations and KPIs will be replicable across EU cities.

Relevance to the Work Programme

ARTEMIS will support the EU's vision for smart cities and its aim of becoming a role model in sustainable development. The researcher's expertise in environmental impact assessment and the supervisor's in smart cities bond effectively to pursue the research plan. The fellowship is a unique opportunity for the researcher to obtain enhanced knowledge and skills on the development of environmental assessment tools and metrics for smart cities.

1. Introduction

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the data management life-cycle of the EU H2020 ARTEMIS project, including all data that will be collected, processed and/or generated within the project activities. In order to make research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR), the DMP outlines (i) how the research data will be handled during and after the end of the project; (ii) what data will be collected, processed and/or generated throughout the project; (iii) which methodologies and standards will be applied across the data management life-cycle; (iv) how the exploitation of data will be promoted, in particular, whether and how data will be shared and/or made accessible in open access (allowing adequate verification and reuse); and (v) how data will be maintained, preserved and curated, during and after the end of the project. Moreover, the DMP provides details on the project's participation in the Open Research Data (ORD) Pilot, which aims at enabling and maximizing accessibility and exploitation of research data generated in H2020 projects. This DMP builds on the H2020 FAIR Data Management Plan Template (the structure of the document in relation to the H2020 FAIR Data Management Plan guidelines is presented in Annex I), and it was prepared and agreed upon by the researcher and the supervisor, with the support of Eurac's Research Support Office, and with contributions from colleagues at the host and at the secondment institution – Eurac Research and Chalmers University of Technology, respectively.

The DMP is a key element of good and sound research data management, and it should be regarded as a living document which goes deeper and offers an increased level of detail and finer granularity as the project progresses. As such, the DMP will be regularly revised and updated over the implementation of the project, to integrate further details and potential significant changes, such as changes in data availability and collection, or changes in data access within the project activities and collaborative work. The document version number and timetable will be updated accordingly (version history and main changes/updates are summarized in Annex II).

2. Data summary

This section summarizes the types of data that will be collected, processed and/or generated, framed under the project objectives and research activities. It briefly describes the data sources, and important aspects regarding access, use and reuse of data from a range of sources, as well as expected data formats and estimated space requirements (data size).

The data collection, analysis, processing and generation within ARTEMIS are directly linked and required to fulfill the project's specific objectives, each addressed in a work package (WP), as outlined in the project proposal:

- to quantify the material and product flows associated with urban systems before & after the implementation of smart city strategies – this objective will be tackled by developing an urban metabolism (UM) model for two cities where smart city strategies have been implemented (WP1);
- to assess how smart city strategies have affected environmental impacts associated with urban activities – this will be tackled by performing a life-cycle assessment (LCA) based on the material and product flows (WP2); and
- to identify the aspects in smart city strategies that can contribute to reducing environmental impacts, and define improved key performance indicators (KPIs) addressing environmental sustainability in smart cities – this objective will be tackled by testing scenarios with the urban UM-LCA framework for improving urban sustainability through the implemented (and new) smart city strategies, with expert and stakeholder involvement (WP3).

2.1. Data collection: purpose, types and relation to research activities

Data collection, which will mostly take place in WP1, during the first 12 months of the project, includes:

- statistical data at international, national, regional and local (municipal) scales, which will be used to characterize material and product flows and develop the material flow accounting (MFA) model, within the UM-LCA framework;
- technical and scientific literature data on product's material composition, lifespan, life-cycle stages and processes, among other details, which will be used to complement statistical data to model and characterize the product flows and respective life-cycles within the UM-LCA framework; and
- project data from the EU smart city projects Stardust (H2020 GA n.°774094) and Sharing Cities (H2020 GA n.°691895), to characterize selected strategies and actions implemented within the projects, and model and analyze consequent changes in the UM-LCA model and to assess their potential environmental benefits and impacts.

In WP2 and WP3, data from scientific and technical literature (e.g., articles, reports) will be used, as well as life-cycle inventory (LCI) data from ecoinvent¹ and/or other LCI databases. The contents, sources, origin and formats of the types of data collected are described below.

The sources, input datasets and methodology for data analysis and processing applied in the UM model will be detailed in the Report 1 of WP1 – *Data collection, UM modelling and preliminary analysis for the two case studies*, in month 12 (August 2022); and the integration with LCI data to develop the UM-LCA model will be detailed in Report 2.1 of WP2 – *Life-cycle modelling for the smart city strategies and selected urban sub-systems*, in month 15 of the project (November 2022).

Statistical data

In brief, statistical data will be collected from international, national, regional and local offices (e.g., Provincia Autonoma di Trento;² Lisboa Aberta;³ on material flows, trade, transportation and waste generation, for example, to build material flow accounting (MFA) models for Lisbon and for Trento. The main sources include publicly available online databases of the international statistics (Eurostat), national statistics organizations/institutes in Portugal and Italy (INE and ISTAT, respectively), the regional statistics office of the Province of Trento (ISPAT) and the Energy and mining analysis and statistics of the Ministry of Ecological Transition. Table 1 summarizes the main statistical data sources and the respective licenses they are framed under. As the project progresses and other datasets and sources are added, the table will be updated.

¹ <https://ecoinvent.org/>

² <https://dati.trentino.it/>

³ <https://lisboaaberta.cm-lisboa.pt>

Table 1 – Statistical data sources and respective licensing frameworks

Source	Licensing framework/summary description
Online database ISTAT (national statistics office in Italy: http://dati.istat.it/)	Data and analysis from the Italian National Institute of Statistics are licensed under a Creative Commons License – Attribution 3.0: they can be copied, distributed, transmitted and freely adapted, even for commercial purposes, provided that the source is acknowledged.
Online database INE (national statistics office in Portugal: https://www.ine.pt/)	The statistical data made available can be used and reused by the users in accordance with the Creative Commons CC BY Attribution 4.0 license provided that the source is acknowledged, as follows: Source: Instituto Nacional de Estatística (INE) – Portugal (identification of the statistical information mentioned; reference period of the information). Users may download or copy documents for personal or commercial use, but Statistics Portugal shall continue to own the respective copyright. Should the user modify the original data, it must be explicitly mentioned.
Online database ISPAT (regional statistics office of the Province of Trento: http://www.statistica.provincia.tn.it/)	Data from the ISPAT database are licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Italia – CC BY 3.0 IT: they can be copied, distributed, transmitted and freely adapted, even for commercial purposes, provided that the source is acknowledged.
Online database MISE (energy-related statistics: https://dgsaie.mise.gov.it/consumi-petroliferi)	The energy and mining analysis and statistics data can be freely reused under the terms of the IODL 2.0 license: the reproduction and dissemination of the data published is authorized on condition that the source is cited.

For the Lisbon case study, the use of statistical microdata is foreseen, which are protected and accessible for research purposes only under a protocol with specific confidentiality and management requirements. Such datasets consist of observation data with high level of disaggregation - e.g., households or establishments – collected by survey, by INE. All datasets are anonymized and include no personal or sensitive details. In this context, a request was submitted to the Direção Geral de Estatísticas da Educação e Ciência (DGEEC). This request was framed under a collaboration established with Dr. Rita Garcia, an experienced researcher in environmental impact assessment from the Association for the Development of Industrial Aerodynamics - Associated Laboratory of Energy, Transports and Aeronautics (ADAI-LAETA), a research non-profit organization associated with the University of Coimbra. Within this protocol, we have requested access to data in the following statistical datasets:

- 1.1 – Inquérito aos orçamentos familiares (Survey on households' expenditure)
- 3.1 – Comércio internacional (International trade)
- 7.1 – Inquérito à estrutura das explorações agrícolas (Survey on the structure of agricultural holdings)
- 8.1 – Inquérito anual à produção industrial (Annual survey on industrial production)
- 15.1 – Inquérito à mobilidade nas áreas metropolitanas de Lisboa e do Porto (Survey on mobility in the metropolitan areas of Lisbon and Oporto)

The purpose of data collected with higher level of disaggregation is to provide further insight on specific material and energy requirements and flows associated with Lisbon, at municipal and metropolitan scale. If and when the request is accepted, a secure access is provided by INE. Datasets provided under this protocol will be kept in a secure physical location (e.g., internal or external hard drive), with no connection to any networks, while the project research activities are being carried out, after which it must be destroyed. Only

the minimum required copies of data should be done, to provide secure access of the identified and authorized researchers only; and the data shall not be printed. All researchers that may have access to the data have been identified (section 2.2) and signed individual statements of compliance with the data management and confidentiality requirements. No need for further statistical data that is not readily and publicly available is foreseen in the project.

Statistical data will be collected mostly in CSV and XLS formats; in cases, PDF files may also be used to collect smaller amounts of data, which will be manually transferred or integrated in CSV files. Statistical raw data collected is expected not to exceed 30 Gb.

Project data

Project (local) data will be collected from the two EU H2020 smart city projects Stardust for Trento (Italy) and Sharing cities for Lisbon (Portugal) to assess how implemented interventions and/or actions have affected urban systems; and, ultimately, to develop the UM-LCA framework (complementing the MFA model), and perform the environmental impact assessment of selected actions of the two projects. An agreement on data access will be signed (for each of the two projects), establishing the terms for access and processing of previously collected data, specifying that only anonymous aggregated data will be accessible. Collected data includes a detailed description of the project actions implemented, as well as data monitored, collected or generated within the projects. Monitored data includes, for example, smart metering data, production, consumption and use data (associated with buildings and/or vehicles), before and/or after the implementation of project actions. Textual-based data on the project actions will be collected in PDF and DOC formats, while quantitative data (including monitored data) will be collected in CSV format. The data size should not exceed 5 Gb.

Data collected within ARTEMIS from the two projects will be processed aggregated data, non-personal, non-sensitive and non-identifiable. Ethics is an integral part of research projects and activities funded by the EU. In line with the EU Regulation No. 1291/2013,⁴ which establishes the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme, both projects – Sharing Cities and Stardust – follow ethical principles and requirements, with particular attention to the protection of personal data. Data protection imposes various obligations, such as to provide research subjects with details on what may happen to (collected) personal data. Personal data collected in Stardust for statistical analysis is collected anonymously, i.e., without association to any names or any other identifiable detail to individuals.

Technical and scientific literature data

Technical and scientific data will be collected through desktop data collection, consisting mostly of scientific journal articles, technical reports and life-cycle inventory datasets/databases, such as ecoinvent. Ecoinvent data is protected under the End User Licence Agreement (EULA)⁵ for ecoinvent Database and ecoinvent Datasets, which restricts the reproduction, dissemination or public display of any significant portions of the ecoinvent Database or the ecoinvent Datasets. Text-based data will be collected in PDF or DOC files, and life-cycle inventory data in XLS or CSV, or in PDF, which will then be manually transferred or integrated into CSV files. The size of technical and scientific literature data is not expected to exceed 2 Gb.

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/legal_basis/fp/h2020-eu-establact_en.pdf

⁵ https://ecoinvent.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/eula-ecoinvent_v2_march_2014.pdf

2.2. Data generation: types of generated data and scientific outputs

Data collection, analysis, modelling and results (generated) in the project will be reported in the following types of scientific outputs:

- model input datasets used to characterize regional and urban material and product flows;
- urban metabolism (MFA) modelling code (Python code incl. data analysis and processing);
- life-cycle inventories - modelling and results;
- a set of KPIs addressing environmental sustainability in smart cities, and recommendations/guidelines for their future development and application (in textual data); and
- scientific publications, including technical reports, peer-reviewed articles in scientific journals, and conference papers.

The research will aim for the highest possible level of transparency, reproducibility and replicability of data and results generated. The selection of materials and methods has been oriented to ensure replicability and scalability. The research findings, data and results should be applicable to other projects, geographical areas and urban systems, to support the design, implementation and evaluation of smart city strategies.

Moreover, data management should improve and maximize access, re-use and exploitation of research data and results generated. All scientific outputs will be made available in open access, together with data needed to validate their contents and results, if and when the licensing and access agreements in place allow. Exceptions may include data collected within restricted/protected frameworks, such as data from scientific journal articles with restricted access,ecoinvent data, statistical microdata, and monitored data from the two case study projects.

Data workflow and management

Drawing on the layered data-engineering convention and on the Kedro project,⁶ data handled in the project will be organized and structured in at least three types: raw, interim/intermediate and processed datasets.

- **Raw data** is source collected data (statistical, project data, etc.) that will be stored in a separate folder to ensure they are unchanged across the whole project implementation. Relevant metadata and other documentation collected on the raw datasets will also be stored.
- **Intermediate data** contain cleansed and/or transformed datasets and source code files, which will be often updated and further processed as the UM-LCA model is developed.
- **Output data** include processed datasets (model input and output datasets) together with source code files, and metadata files and documentations, that will be reported/published and/or archived in public repositories for verification and exploitation (contingent on potential restrictions on collected data sharing, established by licenses, protocols and/or agreements in place).

Source code files used to analyze and process data within the UM-LCA modelling framework will be stored in a public Gitlab repository, together its associated datasets. A Git version control system will be used to handle and keep accurate track and identification of data versioning. The model input and output datasets associated with the UM-LCA framework, with processed data and results on material and product flows, as well as life-cycle inventories, will be made available as open-data, findable and accessible in Zenodo, stored in CSV format files, with column value and data format described in a TXT file, together with the respective metadata (including persistent identifiers) and data documentation, as ReadMe files (see section 4.4). A

⁶ Alam, S., Bălan, L., Comym, G. et al. (2021). Kedro (Version 0.17.6) [Computer software]. <https://github.com/kedro-org/kedro>

Zenodo Community will be created for the project, where all datasets and documents will be accessible through a single collection. The datasets deposited in Gitab and in Zenodo will adopt the standard Data Package format defined and promoted by Frictionless data – a format defined by the Open Knowledge Foundation (OKF), which supports the structuring and definition of metadata (incl. title, description, sources, authors, license, dataset description, meaning of columns, etc.), and uses a data package JSON file to provide it in human and machine-readable format. Scientific outputs and textual data will be stored with open access in traditional data formats, namely DOC and .pdf files for mainly text-based documents (e.g., scientific journal articles, conference papers, presentations, posters). Visualizations may be stored in standard binary (raster image) file formats (e.g., TIF, JPG). The size of the data processed and/or generated within the project, including source code files, datasets and text-based scientific outputs is estimated to reach no more than 15 Gb.

2.3. Data utility

The research data will be made available to researchers and professionals who may be interested in further developing the framework, the modeling code, or applying it to other case studies and datasets. Experts and consultants working with public authorities and policymakers, and companies and businesses in the areas of smart services, can also use the data and results, and apply them to other case studies and datasets, to support decision-making on the design and implementation of smart city strategies.

3. Handling project data: access, security, storage and back-up

Data collected, processed and generated within the project shall be kept on file and stored under secure data space within the facilities of the host institution – Eurac Research – and in a shared online OneDrive folder, during the project duration, with access to authorized people only, i.e., people involved in the research and/or project execution (within Eurac, and the collaborating researchers in partner institutions – ADAI-LAETA and Chalmers). Statistical microdata from INE will be kept only on local storage and copied with physical support (e.g., CD) to share across the researchers, to comply with the conditions of the protocol. Literature data sources, such as scientific journal articles and technical reports will be managed with literature management software Mendeley and/or Zotero. The content of the project webpage is also managed by authorized staff only and based on well-defined rights.

Data protected under specific protocols or agreements, such as statistical microdata and project data collected from H2020 projects Sharing Cities and Stardust will only be accessible to the researchers identified in Table 2. The data handled within the project will not include sensitive nor identifiable data.

Table 2 - Authorized access to all project data
(incl. data protected under confidentiality protocol and/or agreement)

Researcher	Institution
Joana Bastos	Eurac Research
Aaron Estrada	Eurac Research
Gianluca Grazieschi	Eurac Research
Rita Garcia	ADAI-LAETA
Leonardo Rosado	Chalmers University of Technology

ARTEMIS will acquire, process, and model data collected, generated or made available by other researchers, experts and organizations. All project outputs and processed data will be clearly linked to the data inputs and respective sources they derive of. Full credit will be given through citation and/or acknowledgement to the sources, authors and data archives, also to ensure that future users of ARTEMIS outputs will be able to find and access the data used.

Data documentation

The data folders of the project will be structured and organized according to the project main structure and activities (in brief, the following folders will be used: Literature, WP0 - Management, WP1 – UM model, WP2 – LCA, WP3 – KPIs, WP4 – Transfer of knowledge and WP5 – Communication), and all data files will have descriptive and unique names, to ensure coherence and to ease access, such as:

- Scientific and technical literature: First author surname – year (yyyy) - short title/keywords;
- Statistical datasets: Short description/keywords - geographic scale/spatial resolution – year; and
- Text files: Version date (yyyymmdd) - short title – author – contributor of most recent changes.

A ReadMe file will be stored alongside datasets to provide relevant documentation and improve interpretation, accessibility and re-use (further details in section 4.4).

4. Making data FAIR

This section details measures undertaken in ARTEMIS to foster dissemination and exploitation of data and results, through FAIR data principles: making data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable.

4.1. Making data Findable

Data collected, processed and generated in the project will be deposited in Zenodo if and when possible, i.e., complying with conditions of access, use and reproducing collected and/or re-used data, established by the licenses, protocols and/or agreements in place. Deposited data will be identifiable and locatable by means of a clear naming structure and a standard identification mechanism, and it will be made discoverable with metadata. Zenodo automatically makes the link to the OpenAire portal, ensuring findability.

Data naming, references

The naming of datasets and other scientific outputs deposited in public repositories will reflect the contents of the respective product, including (i) project name, (ii) product name (e.g., dataset or article short title), (iii) version, and (iv) date (e.g., date of storage or year of publication). Moreover, to make data discoverable, findable, identifiable and traceable, there will be a record for each dataset and scientific output, for example:

- quantitative datasets - through a unique and identifiable Uniform Resource Locator (URL) provided by git, published and accessible on the GitLab web-platform; and/or
- scientific outputs, such as scientific journal articles – through a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), a unique and persistent identifier.

When adequate, authors' persistent digital identification ORCID will also be used. Clear version numbers will be provided, in all project reports and deliverables, as well as datasets and source code files, as applicable, so that these can be revised, updated and still easily identifiable and traceable.

Metadata

Metadata essentially consists of using descriptors to help reading, tracing, using and managing the scientific outputs (deposited in a repository). The selected repositories for depositing research data in ARTEMIS (GitLab, Zenodo) already have a structure and required fields to compile the document's metadata, namely: (i) title of the project; (i) title of the document/scientific output, (iii) names of authors and/or researchers involved; (iv) institutional affiliation; (v) abstract or summary about the project and/or the data; (v) research topic, or subject of research; (vi) date/year of publication or release; (vii) geographic scope/coverage; (viii) Instrumentation used; (ix) access or rights policies/restrictions/licenses; (x) language; (xi) tags/keywords; and (xii) information on funding framework; among others. As defined in the project Grant Agreement (Article 29.2), the bibliographic metadata will include the terms "Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action", the project name, acronym and grant number, the publication date and a persistent identifier.

Keywords

Search keywords will be used to enable and maximize data findability, re-use and exploitation. Since, to the authors' knowledge, no discipline-specific controlled vocabularies are in place or commonly used in similar types of multidisciplinary research projects, the Library of Congress Subject Headings⁷ will be adopted, with free-form keywords. Keywords will include the name of the project (ARTEMIS) as well as keywords relatable to the project's topics, such as: smart cities, environmental sustainability, urban metabolism, life-cycle assessment, material flow analysis, environmental impacts, key performance indicators, among others.

4.2. Making data openly Accessible

The project will adopt the ORD pilot principle of making research data "*as open as possible, as closed as necessary*". As such, most data collected, processed and generated within the project will be deposited in open repositories, freely accessible to all. For collected data, conditions of licenses, agreements and protocols in place may not allow making data public. In such cases, the source will be clearly mentioned for potential users to be able to find and possibly access (if and when complying with the conditions). Potential restrictions to providing open access to collected data include:

- statistical microdata collected under protocols and/or frameworks that establish confidentiality and data protection conditions;
- data collected from the two case study projects under access agreements that may establish conditions on sharing/reproducing data;
- life-cycle inventory data from ecoinvent or other databases under user agreements that may restrict the reproduction of data; and
- scientific literature journals and other data that may have restricted access and/or sharing conditions.

⁷ <https://id.loc.gov/authorities/subjects.html>

The datasets collected, processed and generated in the project will be deposited on the Zenodo platform, contingent to the restrictions mentioned, in conventional and widely used file formats, namely XLS or CSV. The project will follow the conditions, rules and regulations from the Zenodo repository with regard to accepted way of depositing the data, format, and size of the research data. Source code files developed within the project will be deposited in public Gitlab repositories. The GitLab portal is accessible from anywhere via web browser without any read protection and it provides the ability for bulk download through HTTP or using git without authentication. Both Zenodo and GitLab repositories will remain available beyond the project's duration.

Scientific peer-reviewed journal articles resulting from the project research will be published in Gold Open Access and the final published version, i.e., the Version of Record, will have a digital copy of the full text deposited in the Bolzano Institutional Archive (BIA), following the Open Access Policy adopted by Eurac Research. Public reports and conference proceedings results from the project will also be stored in BIA. BIA is an Institutional Open Access Repository, which stores scientific outputs in full-text and/or their metadata. BIA's structure, facilities and management are in compliance with FAIR data principles. Publications will have clear mention and/or link to associated deposited/archived data. Appropriate arrangements with the repository are already in place as it is the institutional repository of choice within the Open Access Policy⁸ adopted by Eurac Research. Text-based scientific outputs will be made available in conventional and widely used formats such as DOC, PDF, for which a wide range of free software tools is available.

All deposited datasets, source code files and scientific outputs will have the respective link to the respective repository published in Eurac's project webpage.⁹ Relevant documentation to ease interpretation, accessibility and re-used will be stored in ReadMe files, together with datasets (further details in section 4.4). No need for a data access committee is foreseen.

4.3. Making data Interoperable

ARTEMIS is an interdisciplinary research project and no standards for depositing the type of research data and scientific outputs it will collect, process and/or generate exist, to the best of the authors' knowledge. To ease interoperability, data and metadata will build on standards applicable to the statistical datasets (e.g., international classification systems of economic activities, products, materials), existing projects in similar fields and topics, metadata schemes foreseen by selected repositories (e.g., Zenodo), and on the OpenAIRE guidelines.¹⁰ File formats will be selected to improve accessibility (e.g., usable with widely available software). The definition of project-specific ontology or vocabulary schema are not foreseen.

⁸ <https://webassets.eurac.edu/31538/1640258985-eurac-oa-policy-2022.pdf>

⁹ <https://www.eurac.edu/en/institutes-centers/institute-for-renewable-energy/projects/artemis>

¹⁰ <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>

4.4. Increasing data Re-use

As mentioned, datasets will be made available through Zenodo, following the Data Package format, whose main principles are *to be focused, web-oriented, distributed, open, built around existing tools and simple*. Each dataset will be published as a self-contained git repository, following technical specifications of the Data Package format. As such, the repository will include:

- a ReadMe file including information on the dataset title, content description, materials and methods used for data processing and generation, and references to input data sources;
- a datapackage.json file providing information in a machine-friendly format, containing name, title, description, license, homepage, author, contributors and sources; and
- a directory data containing the raw data, preferably in text format (e.g., CSV).

Scientific outputs such as journal articles, conference proceedings and project reports will be deposited in BIA. No embargo period is foreseen for any scientific outputs. All deposited data, in GitLab, Zenodo and BIA, will remain available and re-usable beyond the project duration.

Data license

As mentioned, according to the type of license, agreements and protocols adopted by the publisher / data source, in the case of collected data, there might be restrictions on data sharing. Data generated within the project will be published under an open license (e.g., Creative Commons Zero) to be used, modified and shared by anyone and for any purpose, as defined by the Open Knowledge Foundation in the Open Definition. Each dataset made available in open repositories will provide the specific license of the data both in the ReadMe and in the meta-data JSON file.

Data quality

Data quality will be documented, to ease the selection, interpretation and re-use of data, and potential issues and limitations will be explicitly stated in associated metadata.

5. Costs and allocation of resources

As mentioned, all data and scientific outputs generated in the project will be open for re-use and sharing – no restrictions are foreseen. As for collected data, it will be made available if and when possible, contingent on potential data access and reproducibility conditions. Potential costs related to data management include costs for data acquisition, depositing and/or publication, which are eligible costs as part of the H2020 MSCA fellowship funding – these costs are described next. No costs are foreseen related to preservation of the data beyond the project duration.

Data collection: Statistical data collection will mainly target publicly accessible data – if needed, a limited number of datasets might be purchased. Potential data purchase costs should not exceed 3000€ and, if needed, they will be covered by the H2020 MSCA fellowship funding. LCI background data (ecoinvent) is available and currently used in research projects at Eurac's Institute of Renewable Energy, which covers the associated costs. Regarding project data, literature and technical data collected, no costs are foreseen.

Data archiving/depositing: The project will provide easy access to the research data using free online repositories: BIA, in the case of scientific journal articles and other textual documents; GitLab, in the case of code files and associated datasets; and Zenodo, in the case of output datasets; and all materials will be prepared by the Fellow (and revised by colleagues, when adequate, without any additional costs). As such, data archiving/depositing is not expected to generate any costs.

Publishing: All publications resulting from the project will be published with open access. Scientific articles in peer-reviewed journals will be published under Gold Open Access – two journal articles are foreseen, with potential article publishing charges (APC) between 1000 and 3000€ per article. These costs are eligible within H2020 MSCA grants, under budget category Research, training and networking costs. The costs for printing and preparation of the hardcopy version of the project's leaflet, flyer and booklets are also eligible under the H2020 MSCA fellowship funding.

Data management responsibilities

Eurac Research, the host institution of the MSCA, and the fellow Joana Bastos in particular, will be in charge of data management. Specifically, Eurac will ensure, for example, data quality and completeness; that data deposited in the respective repositories is compliant with the Data Package format; that metadata has quality and completeness to enable access, re-use and exploitation; among others.

6. Data security

To ensure data security, project data will be stored on Eurac's OneDrive, across the whole project duration. Eurac uses state-of-the-art technologies for secure data storage and transfer, as well as for managing the rights of the users (e.g., individuals downloading information from the website). Data on OneDrive is regularly and automatically backed up. Data protected under protocols and/or agreements with increased restrictions on access and storage will be kept in the internal hard drive of the Eurac's notebook allocated to the MSCA Fellow and the authorized researchers (identified in section 3) and have once single a back-up copy in physical external support (e.g., CD). Data will not be transferred using USB drives.

Depositing the data generated and scientific outputs of the project in BIA, GitLab and Zenodo allows for long-term preservation and curation, in compliance with EU guidelines.

7. Ethical and legal aspects

ARTEMIS will not handle personal, sensitive nor identifiable data. The details and clarifications regarding ethics requirements have been addressed in D1.1: POPD Requirement No.1 and D1.2: POPD Requirement No. 2, in the first month of the project.

8. Concluding remarks

This DMP documents the measures and actions to be undertaken to maximize transparency, access, re-use and exploitation of research data associated with the ARTEMIS project. The plan is intended to be a living open document in which further details can be defined and made available as the implementation of the project progresses. As such, the DMP will be revised and updated in M24 and M48 of the project, and if/when significant changes occur (the list of versions and summary and main changes are reported in Annex II).

ANNEX I – Data Management Plan structure in relation to FAIR guidelines

The table below lists the issues that should be addressed in the Data Management Plan, according to the “Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020” (version 3.0, 26 July 2016), together with the section and page addressing them (on the right).

DATA SUMMARY	
State the purpose of data collection and generation. Explain the relation to the objectives of the project.	2. Data summary; p.11
Specify the types and formats of data collected and generated. Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any). Specify the origin of the data. State the expected size of data (if known).	2.1 Data collection: purpose, types and relation to research activities 2.2 Data generation: types of generated data and scientific outputs
Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful	2.3 Data utility
MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA [FAIR DATA]	
Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision). Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers, such as Digital Object Identifiers? Outline naming conventions used. Outline the approach towards search keyword. Outline the approach for clear versioning. Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how.	4.1 Making data Findable
MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE [FAIR DATA]	
Specify which data will be made openly available. If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so. Specify how the data will be made available. Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data. Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g., in open source code)? Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited. Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions.	4.2 Making data Accessible
MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE [FAIR DATA]	
Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability. Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your dataset, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability. If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?	4.3 Making data Interoperable

<p>INCREASE DATA RE-USE (THROUGH CLARIFYING LICENSES) [FAIR DATA]</p>	
<p>Specify how the data will be licensed to permit the widest reuse possible. Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed. Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project. If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why. Describe the data quality assurance process. Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable.</p>	<p>4.4. Increasing data Re-use</p>
<p>ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES</p>	
<p>Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs. Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project. Describe costs and potential value of long-term preservation.</p>	<p>5. Costs and allocation of resources</p>
<p>DATA SECURITY</p>	
<p>Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data</p>	<p>3. Handling project data: access, security, storage and back-up 6. Data security</p>
<p>ETHICAL ASPECTS</p>	
<p>To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former.</p>	<p>7. Ethical and legal aspects</p>
<p>OTHER</p>	<p>n/a</p>

ANNEX II – History of changes and updates to the DMP

Version	Date	Summary of main changes and updates
1.0	04.03.2022	Initial version

